

PROCESSING OF SINGLE-POLYMER COMPOSITES USING THE CONCEPT OF CONSTRAINED FIBRES

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SUMMARY: Nowadays the major trends in polymeric materials focuses on simple mono-component systems, rather than on complex polymer blends. An important reason for this is recyclability. The concept of ‘overheating’ a fibre upon constraining is one of the known methods for manufacturing single polymer composites. This concept was validated on two categories of semi-crystalline polymers: the drawable (i.e. isotactic Polypropylene) and the less drawable ones (i.e. Polyethyleneterephalate and Polyamides). In case of i-PP it was shown that a draw ratio higher than 10 is required in order to obtain a 20 °C shift of the melting temperature and therefore a sufficiently wide processing window. The effect of the post-drawing temperature on the ‘overheating’ behaviour of i-PP was also investigated. It was concluded that the drawing temperature should be optimised in order to avoid relaxation processes in the amorphous phase while at the same time to induce orientation and improvement of the crystals in terms of size and perfection. Less drawable polymers give only a small shift in melting temperature, thus a small processing window. This is mainly due to the low degree of chain-extension, -unfolding of this category of polymers.

KEYWORDS: single polymer composites, drawability, ‘overheating’, processing window, post-drawing conditions

INTRODUCTION

Polymer composites are being used in steadily increasing quantities in diverse fields, e.g. aerospace, automotive, electrical, microelectronics, infrastructure and construction, medical, and chemical industries, as a result of improved material performance, cost-effective production, and manufacturing flexibility (especially the thermoplastics). Compared to the widespread and widely documented activities on polymer recycling, the work on recycling of composites is still modest. However, as composites are more widely used in an increasing number of commodity products, the issue of composite recycling is becoming ever more important. Unfortunately, not all polymers are equally easy to recycle. Since thermoplastics can in theory be re-melted and cooled to solidify an infinite number of times, recycling of thermoplastic composites through material recovery is easier than for thermosets. While this is generally the case, each re-melting unfortunately causes the material to gradually degrade. The presence of additives or inclusions such as glass fibres limits further the application of the recycle as glass-fibre reinforced grades, for example, can only be recycled into new fibre reinforced grades. Hence, there is a need for compatible polymers, which means in practice single-polymer composites.

SINGLE-POLYMER COMPOSITES

The concept of single-polymer composites is not new. Different methods have been proposed in the past for the processing of single-polymer composites, referring mainly to Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP). Mead and Porter presented twenty five years ago the first attempts to prepare single polymer composites using different morphologies of polyethylene as matrix and as reinforcement [1-3]. Since then a lot of effort has been given to employ this concept in real applications. One processing route could be melt- or powder impregnation of multi-filament fibre yarns. Here, the problem will be to prevent melting of fibre while it is being impregnated with a highly viscous polymer melt. This problem is originated from the fact that two materials when combined have the same chemical structure, thus melting temperature. It is to overcome this problem by using different grades of the same material for the matrix

and the reinforcement. Teishev *et al* [2, 3] prepared single polyethylene (PE) composites consisting of high-density PE matrix and ultrahigh molecular-weight PE fibres which have at least a 20°C difference in their melting points. Another very interesting route for the production of single-polymer composites is the hot compaction process devised at the University of Leeds [4]. The same grade of polymer can be used as matrix and reinforcement [5-7] but this route has the drawback of a very small processing window [8], which limits its industrial applicability. Very recently an alternative in the processing of PP fibres in combination with PP resins was achieved using the co-extrusion technology [9]. Basically, the idea is to compact co-extruded fibrous structures consisting of an oriented PP core, which is directly covered with a thin polymer skin, with a lower melting temperature than the core. During consolidation, the co-extrudates are compacted at a temperature in between the melting temperature of the core and the skin, providing a wide processing window.

In order to increase the potential of single-polymer composites it is essential to have polymer fibres and matrices optimised in structure, properties and processing performance. High-performance fibres require highly oriented and extended chains in both, the crystalline and the amorphous phase. This can be achieved by drawing the fibre, as obtained from a low speed melt spinning process, in an additional solid-state post drawing step. Compared to the bulk material, drawn fibres can exhibit a shift of the melting temperature and an increased enthalpy of melting. As mentioned above, the production of single-polymer composite demands a clear difference in the melting temperatures of the fibre and matrix materials. If the same grade of polymer is used for the matrix and the reinforcement, the shift in the melting temperature of the drawn fibre is not always sufficient enough for the production of single-polymer composites. It has been reported that the constraining of a PE and PP reinforcing fibre results in a further shift of the melting temperature to a higher value allowing a wider processing window for the single-polymer composite [10-14]. This enables to impregnate a bundle of constrained polymer fibre/tape with a matrix of the same grade without melting of the fibre. The concept of constraining a polymer-reinforcing element will be discussed in details in the next paragraph.

The concept of constrained fibres

In order to obtain a workable processing window for single-polymer composites, the difference in melting temperature between fibre and matrix has to be sufficiently high. The ‘overheating’ behaviour of constrained fibres has been reported for gel-spun PE [10] and gel-spun isotactic PP (i-PP) [11], and for melt-spun i-PP fibres and films [12,13], but in the latter studies only melting temperature shifts of about 10°C have been observed. Compared with isotropic PE and i-PP, unconstrained drawn fibres exhibit usually only a small shift of the melting temperature and an increased enthalpy of melting, which can be assigned to an increase of crystallinity caused by stress-induced recrystallisation during the solid-state drawing process. Constraining the same fibre, results in a further shift of the melting temperature to higher temperatures and a further increased melting enthalpy. The shift in melting temperature (T_m) results from an entropy effect. It is well known that unconstrained and constrained fibres have the same enthalpy of melting (ΔH), while the constraining reduces the gain in entropy per monomer unit (ΔS) [15]. Since $T_m = \Delta H / \Delta S$ and ΔS is increasing upon molecular orientation, T_m shifts towards higher temperatures. Consequently the oriented chains in the fibre can not melt when the fibre is constrained in a matrix, viz. adopt a random coil conformation. This demands highly extended chains and low chain mobility. It is difficult for instance to achieve a high degree of ‘overheating’ for PE. PE possesses different crystal structures. Next to the standard orthorhombic structure a hexagonal phase, which is a so-called “mobile” phase, exists. The orthorhombic structure in PE fibres transforms in the hexagonal crystal structure above 155 °C. In the hexagonal phase the chain mobility is high and the fibre can not sustain any load and, consequently, the fibre fails. This situation occurs only upon constrained heating.

The chain extensibility of some polymers is also questionable. The drawability is associated with the existence of interactions between the chains. Polymers possessing strong secondary bonds (hydrogen bonds) form folded-chain crystals which are barrier for ultra-drawing, since the crystals can not be unfolded. In respect to their drawability, semicrystalline polymers can be classified in two groups, i.e. the highly drawable polymers and the poorly drawable ones [16-18]. The drawability of these polymers

depends mainly on their chain mobility and is associated to the presence or absence of a crystalline α_c -relaxation [18]. i-PP belongs to the first category with draw ratios >14. On the other hand nylons (PA6, PA66 etc.) and PET are termed as 'crystal-fixed' and show limited drawability. The spinning and post-drawing conditions (take up speeds and post-drawing temperature, respectively) play an important role for the ultimate draw ratio and the degree of chain orientation of a polymer. Nevertheless, there are cases where only low draw ratios < 14 can be obtained.

A very recent study considers the effect of the post-drawing conditions on the morphology and mechanical properties of i-PP fibres [19]. It was concluded that the drawing conditions affect both the morphology and the orientation of the induced crystals. It is not known however, how much this parameter influences the shift of the melting temperature. A second related issue deals with the applicability of the concept of constraining in case of polymers with limited drawability. A first aim of this work was therefore to investigate the effect of the drawing conditions on the degree of 'overheating' on the example of drawable i-PP fibres. A further scope of this study was to apply the idea of 'overheating' to less-drawable polymers like Polyamide (e.g. PA6) and Polyester (e.g. Polyethyleneterephalate (PET)) in order to investigate the potential of the constraining concept in both drawable and 'crystal-fixed' polymers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The commercial iPP grade used in this study was X7284, kindly provided by DSM, The Netherlands, which has an average molecular weight of 280 kg/mol and a melt flow index of 13. The PA6 grade was Ultramid[®] BS 3300 provided by BASF, Germany and the PET was a commercial fibre grade provided by Acordis, The Netherlands. All materials were provided in pellet form. Before spinning, the PA6 and PET pellets were dried in a vacuum oven at 150°C for at least 24 hr. The fibres were prepared using a home-built lab-scale melt-spinning device, which consisted of a double walled storage cylinder, which could accommodate about 10 g of material (see Fig. 1). The spinning temperatures were 200, 250 and 290 °C for PP, PA6 and PET, respectively. The spinning device was equipped with a capillary of 1.5 mm diameter and a length of 8 mm. The fibres were wound on a drum at rates varying from 5 to 120 m/min. The next step in the fibre preparation procedure was solid state drawing of the filaments. Solid state drawing was performed using a home-built stretching unit, consisting of two small drums of 48.5 mm diameter separated by a 600 mm long ceramic oven which is schematically presented in Fig. 2. Absolute speed, speed ratio of the two drums and temperature are computer controlled. The PP fibres were post-drawn at temperatures varying between 70 and 200 °C with draw ratios (speed relation of the two wheels of the drawing unit) varying between 2 and 14. The PA6 and PET fibres were post-drawn at different temperatures between their glass transition temperature (T_g) and their melting temperature in order to obtain max draw ratios.

The calorimetric measurements were performed using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7 apparatus. The fibres were either placed unconstrained in the aluminium pans or wound on an aluminium rod to keep them constrained during heating. A heating rate of 10 °C/min was used throughout this study. For the production of single-fibre model composites both ends of the polymer fibres were fixed on glass slides in order to prevent relaxation during heating. Pellets from the same polymer grade were isothermally hot pressed. The resulting thin films were placed on the same glass slide as the fibre. These stacked samples were heated in a hot-stage, melting only the matrix material but not the constrained fibre. Afterwards, the samples were either air-cooled or isothermally crystallised in a gradient hot-stage. The investigation of the composite morphology was performed using a transmission light microscope (Zeiss Universal) equipped with crossed polarisers.

Figure 1: Home-built lab-scale melt-spinning device

Figure 2: Home-built stretching unit (schematically presented)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3a shows the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) heating traces of an unconstrained and a constrained highly oriented i-PP fibre (draw ratio of 10) [14]. The difference in the melting temperature of the unconstrained and constrained fibre is higher than 20 °C, which allows for the preparation of single fibre model composites by embedding the constrained fibre in thin films of a matrix based on the same i-PP grade (see Fig. 3b). Fig. 3b presents a sample, which was isothermally crystallised at 145 °C for 3 days. Three different regions are observable: (i) The i-PP fibre partially embedded in (ii) a transcrystalline layer, surrounded by (iii) the i-PP matrix material consisting of spherulitic superstructures. Beside the shift in the melting point, this picture provides a proof of principle that the concept of constraining can be used to prepare single polymer composites in case of i-PP.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: (a) DSC curve of an unconstrained and constrained polymer fibre showing the increase in melting temperature, (b) micrograph of single polymer fibre based on a constrained oriented polymer fibre impregnated with an unconstrained non-oriented polymer matrix of the same grade as the fibre.

As mentioned above, the effect of ‘overheating’ becomes more pronounced with increasing chain orientation. The post-drawing conditions should be optimised, in order to prevent relaxation processes in

the amorphous phase while at the same time induce orientation and improvement of the crystals in terms of size and perfection.

Fig. 4a and 4b show DSC-measurements, of unconstrained and constrained chopped i-PP fibres, respectively. Five different temperatures between 70 and 200 °C were selected to post-draw the i-PP fibres, while a constant post-draw ratio of 7 was applied. When drawn at low temperatures, unconstrained samples (see Fig. 4a) show one melting peak which is shifting towards higher temperatures. Fibres drawn at 160 and 200°C present a shift of their melting peak back to lower temperatures. Constrained samples (see Fig. 2b) give a similar picture. At low drawing temperatures, double melting peaks are deduced. Several studies report on multiple peaks in i-PP. These peaks can be explained by the presence of two morphological forms (i.e. lamellar and fibrillar morphology in the same sample). Furthermore, the effect of ‘overheating’ becomes less effective at drawing temperatures higher than 145°C, exactly as in case of unconstrained fibres.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Influence of the post-drawing temperature on the ‘overheating’ behaviour of: (a) an unconstrained i-PP fibre (b) a constrained i-PP fibre. Note: The draw ratio in both cases is 7.

The aforementioned behaviour of constrained and unconstrained fibres can be explained as follows: At low post drawing temperatures (up to 145°C), the molecular mobility in the crystals is too low for effective relaxation processed on the time scale of the deformation process (affine deformation). This increases the stiffness of the amorphous phase. The applied stress can be effectively transferred via the stiff amorphous phase into the crystal phase resulting in shearing and final fragmentation of the lamellae into small crystal blocks. It can be concluded that at low post drawing temperatures the morphology consists of small and imperfect crystals kept highly oriented by the constrained amorphous phase. At higher post drawing temperatures, the chain mobility in the crystals is increased. Relaxation processes directly accompany the deformation of the amorphous phase; i.e. the applied stress cannot effectively be transferred to the crystals, which results in less fragmentation of the lamellae. Furthermore, the high mobility of the polymer chains at elevated post drawing temperatures allows perfection and growth of the crystals. However, the ineffective stress-transfer to crystals via ‘soft’ amorphous phase results in a reduced orientation of the crystal phase with respect to the drawing direction. Consequently, the shift in melting temperature of unconstrained fibres mainly originates from the growth and perfection of the crystals. In case of constrained fibres, both the orientation and the crystals morphology play an important role in the ‘overheating effect’.

Fig. 5a and 5b show the effect of draw ratio on the ‘overheating’ behaviour, of unconstrained and constrained i-PP fibres, respectively. It is shown in Fig. 4a and 4b that at post-drawing temperatures above 145°C relaxation processes take place and this temperature gives the maximum gain in terms of ‘overheating’. Therefore, the post drawing temperature was kept constant at 145°C and different draw ratios, varying between 2 and 14 were applied. In case of unconstrained samples the draw ratio seems to influence only the shape of the melting peak and not the absolute melting point (see Fig. 5a). Low draw ratios give more narrow peaks. As the draw ratio is increasing the melting peaks become wider, but there is no shift in the melting point. Constrained specimens with draw ratios up to 10, present only a slight shift in their melting point. On the contrary, highly drawn constrained specimens (draw ratio of 14) (see fig. 5b) present a further shift of more than 10°C. This behaviour was expected, since the orientation of the chains induced at high draw ratios can be beneficial under constraining, but disappears when the specimen is free to shrink upon melting. On the other hand, the draw ratio does not influence directly the morphology of the induced crystals, therefore there is no change in the melting point of the unconstrained samples.

Figure 5: Influence of the ultimate draw ratio on the ‘overheating’ behaviour of: (a) an unconstrained i-PP fibre (b) a constrained i-PP fibre. Note: The post-drawing temperature in both cases is 145 °C.

Fig. 6a and 6b show the DSC traces, of constrained and unconstrained PET and PA6 fibres, respectively. The fibres were drawn to their maximum draw ratio, which was in both cases approximately 4. A shift of 8 to 10 °C of the melting point of the fibres was observed upon constraining. This small shift is due to the limited drawability of both polymers. This means in practice, that the polymer chains are still folded, and increased entropy, thus an ‘overheating’ effect can not be achieved. A recent review article on the ultradrawability of polymers [18] states that all semicrystalline polymers can be drawn to draw ratios of 3, but further (hot) drawing is only possible for polymers with an α_c -relaxation and sufficiently low level of entanglements. Nevertheless, several trials have been made to enhance the drawability of ‘crystal-fixed’ systems. In PET and to lesser extent in nylons, low initial crystallinity and crystallisation during drawing can be exploited to achieve draw ratios >5 [18]. Multiple-stage drawing processes [20], zone-drawing and zone-annealing processes [21-23] and other post-treatment methods [24] have been employed on PET and nylons. The general conclusion is that slightly improvements can be obtained, but no processing route has yet been devised to impart a structure of highly oriented, predominately crystalline fibres with crystal continuity. It can be concluded, that the constraining concept is not so efficient in case of poorly drawable polymers. The hot compaction route has been already used for making single PET composites [5]. The PET fibres were annealed at different temperatures, nevertheless the resulted processing window was not wider than 10 °C.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Effect of constraining on the ‘overheating’ behaviour of: (a) PET fibre (b) PA6 fibre. Note: For both cases, the post-drawing temperature is 90 °C and the draw ratio is 4.

CONCLUSIONS

It was shown in this study, that in order to have a wide processing window for manufacturing of single-polymer composites two prerequisites should be fulfilled: a) the drawing temperature should be optimised in order to avoid relaxation processes in the amorphous phase while at the same time induce orientation and improvement of the crystals in terms of size and perfection, b) the draw ratio should be high enough (above 7) in order to have chain unfolding and perfectly oriented. The second condition does not easily apply on poorly drawable polymers; therefore constraining of these fibres can not be effective enough to create a wide processing window. The combination of the constraining concept with that of co-extrusion is an alternative for poorly drawable polymer.

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